

DATA MANAGEMENT SYSTEM APPLIED TO PORT TERMINAL MAINTENANCE

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Summary- In the industrial sector, data maps processes and resolves internal bottlenecks, identifying obstacles affecting operational performance. This work presents the development of a system focused on maintaining a port terminal, relating data collected during corrective maintenance with information on the failure mode, allowing the enhancement of understanding capacity and speed of failure containment, defect detection, and strategic mapping for maintenance planning and control.

Keywords: Maintenance management; Process Computerization; Terminal Maintenance; Data analysis.

Figure 1 – Cargo receipt and shipment cycle [1]

INTRODUCTION

In the sixties, globalization and the search for greater productivity led companies to adopt multiple work shifts. This led to an emphasis on equipment availability, reducing machine repair time and increasing the impact of corrective maintenance on the process since the competitiveness, productivity, and efficiency of these facilities are greatly conditioned by the performance of the equipment [1].

With operations occurring continuously, it becomes necessary to define strategies so that the equipment operates within the required standard.

The most accurate way to choose and define a strategy is to make it based on data, enabling a deeper study of the current scenario. As a result, information from organizations' internal and external environments becomes crucial in any decision-making process [2].

It is common to find processes that still work completely manually, continue to operate without a bias towards major technological innovations, and often even with obsolete systems.

The Port of Santos, located in the Baixada Santista region of São Paulo, is defined by ROCHA [3] as a Conventional Port. In Brazil, such ports are generally found in urban, metropolitan environments built between the 16th and 20th centuries. Over time, these facilities have been partially improved, but many of them suffer from technological lags.

This research work had as a case study company a Bulk Terminal located in the port of Santos whose activity involves receiving bulk cargo (sugar, corn, and soybeans) coming by train and truck transport, temporary storage, and then shipment to other countries on ships of different sizes, and the process is shown in Fig. 1.

The information generated during shutdowns for corrective maintenance of equipment is primary and essential data for identifying bottlenecks, such as more problematic equipment, more recurrent failure modes, and the like [4]. In the Terminal studied, there is enormous difficulty and inefficiency in collecting, storing, structuring, analyzing, and dealing with these.

Much of this results from a completely manual and non-standardized recording system, which depends on feedback from spreadsheets, an outdated history, centralized information in specific collaborators and unstructured communication.

Given these conditions, the proposed work is the development of a data collection and management system based on SaaS (Software as a Service), providing continuous improvement with gains in the allocation of financial and human resources and the creation of a structured historical base, as well as analysis tools that can be applied in reliability gain and activity optimization studies.

DEVELOPMENT

TAURION [5] defines the concept of Big Data as the storage of large volumes of data and as an ecosystem encompassing several technologies so that companies can extract maximum value from information for their business.

Following this reasoning, this work aims to enable the maintenance of a port terminal and related areas to use the data generated within its process efficiently.

Maintenance activities exist to prevent any equipment or installations' natural or non-natural degradation. As this area has a strong relationship with the productive sectors, especially in terms of quality and productivity, it plays a fundamental strategic role in improving businesses' operational and financial results [6].

In this way, storing everything done for maintenance allows area leaders to assess what needs to be done and identify possible errors in executing the related steps.

The study in [7] shows that automation has played a fundamental role in business environments, using its resources to process the information necessary for

decision-making. How information is obtained, organized, recorded, retrieved, and subsequently used allows us to act more safely, increasing the possibility of correct decision-making.

They also argue that regardless of the aspect of the decision, this attitude must be the result of a systematized process, which involves the study of the problem based on data collection, production of information, establishment of solution proposals, choice of decision, feasibility and implementation decision making and analysis of the results obtained. For the study, they considered an information system to be the entire set of data and information organized in an integrated manner to meet demand and anticipate user needs.

For the development of the presented system, SaaS (Software as Service) applications from the Microsoft Power Platform were chosen, characterized by easy usability, self-integration, and connectors, which allow the connection of applications, data, and devices in the cloud as shown in Fig. 2.

Figure 2 – Tools and applications [2].

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The flowchart in Fig. 3 shows the processing of the Data Management system applied to Port Terminal maintenance.

Figure 3 – System flowchart [3].

Shipment/Receiving: are the processes carried out within the Terminal.

Failure is defined by an asset's inability to perform its function, making the process impossible or damaging. When a failure occurs, the maintenance team is called to evaluate it.

Data input: When called, the maintenance team performs the service and reports the relevant information.

Storage: The information collected is stored in cloud databases.

Data visualization: The BI dashboards are updated when new data enters the database.

Data analysis: As soon as the algorithm detects a new data input, it performs analysis and makes decisions based on triggers found.

Start failure analysis report process: When necessary, data is shared between the bases so that the relevant occurrence information related to the Failure Analysis Reports is present in the database.

Help chain: All system flows make up the help chain, whether responsible for releasing insights, updating dashboards, sharing data, or making decisions.

The system can be classified into modules, as shown in Fig. 4.

Figure 4 – System Diagram [4].

Specifying, we have:

- **Application:** In this layer, we have the applications where data inputs are made. There are two, one aimed at recording maintenance occurrences and the other for developing Failure Analysis Reports (RAF).

- **Database:** where the databases are concentrated. They are allocated in the cloud and divided into lists.

- **Automatic Flows:** responsible for the entire aid chain.

- **Analysis and Management:** a layer of instruments that dynamically visualize information, manage actions, and send insights.

For better stratification and application of the data collected during the process, the MIT (Massachusetts Institute of Technology) standard for maintenance was used in the equipment division, represented by Fig. 5, which allows us to expand the input and subsequent visualization of the information.

Figure 5 – Equipment division structure [5].

The information collected is processed and arranged dynamically using Business Intelligence.

Some of the reports generated by the developed system are shown in Fig. 6 and Fig. 7.

Figure 6 – Systemic Loss Report [6].

Figure 7 – Systemic Loss Report [7].

This work explored maintenance needs in the context of historical recording and subsequent data analysis.

Digitalizing processes and automating tasks enabled productivity gains and reduced costs with the best allocation of time, resources, and people and the standardization of information. There is also an improvement in integration between sectors, which are interconnected and aligned and begin to carry out a production cycle that is very beneficial for the present and future of the organization.

All modules developed and described throughout the work were validated and implemented within the Terminal, becoming part of the routine of maintenance-oriented sectors, thus implementing the data-driven decision culture, which is defined by KUMAR [7] as a term used to indicate that decision-making is based on the analysis of actual data and the use of defined metrics to guide strategic decisions focused on the company's business objectives and goals.

As a prospect for the system, one can consider the integration of IoT (Internet of Things) through smart sensors, devices capable of collecting historical data from machines, and building models to predict when equipment components may fail, anticipating the undue stops. This also reduces the dependence on data entry on the part of employees.

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